

Effect of fertilizers and green manure on yield of detached deepwater rice plants grown in water.

Treatment	Yield (g m ⁻² tank area)	
	Grain	Straw
No fertilizer (control)	14.4	261
5 ppm N as urea	25.1	321
10 ppm N as urea	27.4	329
5 ppm N through fresh <i>Sesbania aculeata</i> plants (3 kg)	22.6	326
5 ppm N as urea and 5 ppm P ₂ O ₅ as single superphosphate	37.5	394
5 ppm N as urea, 5 ppm P ₂ O ₅ as single superphosphate, and 5 ppm K ₂ O as muriate of potash	38.7	378
LSD (0.05)	6.9	39.5

of N alone, either through urea or green manure. The detached plants could complete their life cycle to grain filling and ripening without anchorage and nutrition from the soil. However, grain yield was low, with a maximum harvest index of 0.1. ■

Integrated N management with *Gliricidia maculata* and *Sesbania aculeata* for transplanted rice

L. S. Chavan, B. P. Patil, and T. S. Ingole, Agricultural Research Station, Palghar 401404, Thane District, Maharashtra, India

To save on fertilizer costs, green manure (GM) is used in conjunction with fertilizer N. We evaluated the effect of integrating GM *Gliricidia maculata* and *Sesbania aculeata* with different levels of fertilizer N (urea) on grain yield of transplanted rice in the 1989-90 rainy season. *Gliricidia* seedlings were planted on ricefield bunds at a distance of 0.5-1 m. The plants produced sufficient green loppings after 3 yr with 2.74% N, 0.5% P, and 1.1 % K in the leaves (dry weight basis). *Sesbania* was grown in situ at a seeding rate of 50 kg ha⁻¹ and incorporated in the soil after 45 d. *Sesbania* contained 2.9% N, 0.2% P, and 0.98% K. Soil was clay with pH 8.1, 0.6% organic C, and 200-42-346 kg available NPK ha⁻¹.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. GM crops were incorporated in the soil at transplanting. On the same day, 30-

Effect of green manure and fertilizer N on rice yield and comparative economic data. Maharashtra, India.

Treatment	Rice yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Cost of cultivation (US\$ ha ⁻¹)	Gross returns (US\$ ha ⁻¹)	Net returns (US\$ ha ⁻¹)	B:C ^a
	1989	1990	Pooled mean				
100 kg N ha ⁻¹ as urea in 3 splits: 1/2 at planting + 1/4 at tillering + 1/4 at panicle initiation (recommended)	3.6	2.6	3.1	344.99	404.71	59.72	1.17
5 t <i>G. maculata</i> ha ⁻¹ (27.4 kg N ha ⁻¹) + 50 kg N ha ⁻¹ as urea at planting	3.1	2.2	2.6	330.10	342.95	12.85	1.04
7.5 t <i>G. maculata</i> ha ⁻¹ (41.1 kg N ha ⁻¹) + 25 kg N ha ⁻¹ as urea at planting	3.4	2.5	2.9	334.80	385.00	50.20	1.15
5 t <i>S. aculeata</i> ha ⁻¹ (29 kg N ha ⁻¹) + 50 kg N ha ⁻¹ as urea at planting	3.2	2.3	2.8	335.70	363.98	28.28	1.08
7.5 t <i>S. aculeata</i> ha ⁻¹ (43.5 kg N ha ⁻¹) + 25 kg N ha ⁻¹ as urea at planting	3.4	2.1	2.7	333.35	357.41	24.06	1.07
Control (no N)	2.4	1.5	1.9	301.46	253.60	-47.86	0.84
SE±	0.2	0.2	0.1				
LSD (0.05)	0.6	0.5	0.2				

^aBenefit-cost ratio.

to 35-d-old seedlings of 125-d-duration rice variety PLG1 were transplanted. P and K at 50 kg ha⁻¹ each were basally applied. N was applied as per treatment schedule (see table).

Fertilizer application at the recommended dose and integration of fertilizer N with GM proved superior to the control. Basal application of 7.5 t *G. maculata* with 25 kg urea N ha⁻¹ was on par with 100 kg urea N ha⁻¹ in terms of yield. Costs of cultivation, gross returns, net returns, and benefit-cost ratio of this integrated N management treatment were comparable with those of the recommended dose. With this treatment, a savings of 75 kg urea N ha⁻¹ may be achieved. ■

Fertilizer management— inorganic sources

Response of late-transplanted rice to NPK under irrigated conditions

B. Hasan, A. S. Bali, and K. N. Singh, Agronomy Division, S. K. University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology (SKUAST), P. O. Box 706, G. P. O. Srinagar, Kashmir 180001, India

Rice followed by rapeseed - mustard is the most feasible double cropping system in Kashmir Valley (1650 m asl). But aberrant weather conditions (low temperature and cloudiness) delay transplanting. The NPK requirement of a crop under such a situation may differ from that of a timely planted rice crop, which usually requires 80-45-20 kg NPK ha⁻¹.

We conducted a 2-yr field trial at SKUAST's Shalimar Campus, on silty clay loam soil (pH 6.8, low available N and P, medium available K) during the 1990-91 wet seasons. The 18 treatments, tested in a randomized block design experiment with three replications, comprised different combinations of NPK levels (see table). Half the N and a full P and K dose were applied basally while the remaining N was applied in two splits: at tillering (18 d after transplanting [DAT]) and at panicle initiation (37 DAT).

Rice variety K39 was transplanted at 15 × 1.5-cm spacing at 3 seedlings per hill by the 1st week of Jul. During the experiment, temperatures ranged from 23.0 to 31.1 °C (maximum) and from 11.3 to 19.6 °C (minimum). Relative humidity was 45-76%. Total rainfall averaged 234 mm, spread over 35 d.

Effect of NPK levels on yield and yield-attributing characters of rice. Kashmir, India. 1990-91.

Nutrient level (kg ha ⁻¹)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	1,000-grain weight (g)
N				
40	4.0	318	57.8	21.25
80	4.5	331	65.8	21.70
120	4.7	339	69.0	23.05
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.37	5	1.7	0.50
P				
8.8	3.6	315	58.7	20.90
17.6	4.6	331	64.7	21.50
26.4	5.0	344	69.0	22.15
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.37	5	1.7	0.50
K				
16.6	4.9	322	63.0	21.40
33.2	5.5	335	65.4	21.65
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.30	4	1.3	0.40

Results showed that up to 80 kg of N and up to 26.4 kg of P ha⁻¹ significantly increased rice grain yield with concomitant improvement in all yield attributes (see table). The yield levels obtained were, however, lower than those of a timely sown crop (5.5 - 6.0 t ha⁻¹). This implies that a combination of 80-26.4-33.2 kg NPK ha⁻¹ will give satisfactory yields under late transplanting conditions in the valley. ■

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Evaluating stem-nodulating green manure crops for lowland rice

D. N. Medhi, Agronomy Department, Assam Agricultural University (AAU), Jorhat 785012, Assam, India; and B. Deka Medhi, Agricultural Chemistry Research Unit, AAU

We studied the effect of stem-nodulating green manure (GM) crops *Sesbania rostrata*, *S. speciosa*, *Aeschynomene afraspera*, *A. indica*, *A. schemperi*, and *A. nilotica* on N₂ fixation and biomass production in lowland rice. The experiment was conducted during Aug 1993 and Jul 1994 wet season on a sandy loam acidic soil (pH 5.1) with 205 kg available N ha⁻¹. *S. aculeata* was the check.

Treatments were replicated four times in a randomized block design. The GM seeds were broadcast at 50 kg ha⁻¹ in all the 3 × 3-m plots. The GM plants were allowed to grow for 45 d after emergence; they were then cut at ground level from an area of 0.32 m² in each plot. N concentration of the whole plants was determined by micro-Kjeldahl method.

Significant differences in dry biomass production, N concentration, and N content of the GM crop were recorded (see table). *S. rostrata* and *A. afraspera* were found to be superior to all other species, indicating that these two are the most suitable GM crops for lowland rice soils. ■

Dry biomass production, N concentration, and N content of different green manure crops. Assam, India, 1993-94.

Species	Dry biomass (t ha ⁻¹)		N concentration (%)		N content (kg ha ⁻¹)	
	1993	1994	1993	1994	1993	1994
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i>	3.1	3.2	1.4	1.5	41	44
<i>Sesbania rostrata</i>	5.3	6.1	3.0	3.2	142	188
<i>Sesbania speciosa</i>	3.1	3.3	2.7	2.9	94	88
<i>Aeschynomene afraspera</i>	4.3	5.4	3.6	3.8	139	185
<i>Aeschynomene indica</i>	2.5	3.1	2.7	2.9	65	89
<i>Aeschynomene schemperi</i>	2.3	2.2	2.8	2.8	61	58
<i>Aeschynomene nilotica</i>	2.4	3.5	2.6	2.7	61	84
LSD (0.05)	2.5	2.3	1.8	1.9	30	32

Managing crop residue in rice

R. D. Misra, V. K. Gupta, and D. S. Pandey, Department of Agronomy, G. E. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology (GBPUAT), Pantnagar, Nainital 263145, India

Burning of crop leads to loss of organic matter and nutrients. Incorporating straw helps in nutrient recycling and maintains soil health. We carried out an experiment on crop residue management at GBPUAT, Pantnagar, during the 1993-94 kharif season.

Soil was loam with pH 7.4, 0.084% total N, 1.10% organic C, 17.0 kg available P ha⁻¹, and 194.0 kg available K ha⁻¹. The experiment, laid out in randomized block design, had 12 treatments with four replications, (see table).

Green manure (GM) crop *Sesbania aculeata* was grown and incorporated in the Same plot before transplanting rice, This provided 60 kg excess N ha⁻¹ in 1993 and 57 kg excess N ha⁻¹ in 1994. Berseem (*Trifolium alexandrinum* L.) was sown in a standing crop of rice at the milk stage and was incorporated in the field 1 mo before transplanting, giving an additional 80 and 70 kg N ha⁻¹ in the respective years. Incorporation of wheat straw, done without a starter dose, provided an additional 74 and 65 kg N ha⁻¹. With 20 kg of starter dose of N (as urea), straw incorporation provided